

Clinical role of *Helicobacter pylori* infection and eradication in the development of gastric cancer

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Since *Helicobacter pylori* (*H. pylori*), the gastric bacterium, was discovered by Dr. Marshall and Dr. Warren in 1982 [1], and its medical importance and relevance to gastric cancer determined, many research about the relationship between *H. pylori* and gastric cancer has been done. The genome sequencing of *H. pylori* was completed in 1997 [2]. Based on these results, further research regarding the carcinogenic mechanism of gastric cancer concerning *H. pylori* infection have been advanced. In 1994, the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) classified *H. pylori* as a type 1 carcinogen (that is definite; the same designation as used for smoking) for gastric cancer based on evidence from a series of large-scale epidemiological studies. *H. pylori* is the only one of many bacteria currently known that can cause a human malignant tumor. *H. pylori* infection is now acknowledged as a main acquired factor involved in the pathogenesis of peptic ulcers, chronic gastritis, and gastric cancer [3].

Gastric cancer follows lung cancer as the most common cause of cancer mortality worldwide. Although surgical resection is still the primary therapeutic strategy for gastric cancer, overall survival has steadily improved as the result of the development of various other treatment options, such as chemotherapy, radiotherapy and endoscopic intervention.

From a global perspective, there are significant geographical variations in incidence of gastric cancer [4]. Two-thirds of gastric cancer cases occur in countries with inferior economic development. Also, gastric cancer remains one of the most frequent gastrointestinal cancers in Eastern Asian. Japan is one of the countries which has the highest global gastric cancer incidence rate. The incidence of gastric cancer in Japan is approximately eight fold higher than in the US. This variation may be partially explained by differences in the socioeconomic background of the groups. While several studies have demonstrated a link between the incidence of gastric cancer and socioeconomic status, high gastric cancer incidence in Asian populations including Japan appears to involve a high infection rate of *H. pylori*.

The pathogenesis of *H. pylori* infection in gastric cancer development can vary according to anatomical location. A meta-analysis of 12 prospective cohort studies demonstrated that *H.*

pylori infection is a risk factor for non-proximal cancer, but not for proximal cancer (odds ratio (OR): 2.97, 95% confidence interval: 2.34-3.77) [5]. There was no such significant difference in prevalence of *H. pylori* infection between histological subtypes or between the intestinal- and diffuse-type gastric cancers. In intestinal-type gastric cancer, there was a theoretical explanation of the cancerization process. Correa et al. suggested a model in which a cumulative process of precancerous change led to the development of intestinal-type gastric cancer. This cancerization process is initiated by superficial gastritis triggered by chronic *H. pylori* infection. Although it is difficult to verify this model in humans, the process has been reproduced in animal experiments using rodent models [6-8].

H. pylori eradication has been shown to have a prophylactic effect on gastric cancer in rodent models [9-11]. However, studies on *H. pylori* eradication in humans have shown less consistent results. Meanwhile it has been reported previously that prophylactic eradication of *H. pylori* after endoscopic resection of early gastric cancer should be used to prevent the development of metachronous gastric cancer [12]. Further analysis with follow up of 3-8.5 years demonstrated a significant reduction in cancer incidence after *H. pylori* eradication [13]. Indeed, a large prospective study (mean follow-up of 9.4 years) also proposed that *H. pylori* eradication before the development of intestinal metaplasia is probably effective in reducing gastric cancer incidence [14].

Suzuki, et al. reported that nonphosphorylated CagA, a major virulence factor of *H. pylori*, activity contributes to the epithelial proliferative and proinflammatory responses associated with development of chronic gastritis and gastric cancer [15]. In addition, it is recognized that *H. pylori*-induced atrophic gastritis with suppressed acid secretion reduces the risk of gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD). As expected, an inverse relationship has been reported between *H. pylori* infection and the development of proximal gastric and esophageal adenocarcinomas. However, controversy still exists regarding the preventative effect of *H. pylori* infection for esophagitis and its carcinogenic sequelae. Several studies reported that eradication of *H. pylori* did not increase the risk of esophagitis, proximal gastric or esophageal adenocarcinoma [16].

According to the most recent report, *H. pylori* eradication therapy is associated with improvement of dyspeptic symptoms in patients with functional dyspepsia (FD), which is consistently demonstrated in the Asian, European, and American populations [17].

Further clarification of both the relevance of *H. pylori* to gastric cancer, and the role of *H. pylori* eradication and other therapies in the prevention of gastric cancer continue to be desired.

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